

Experimental

Melting points are determined by capillary method and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded in KBr on I.R.—20 (Beckmann).

3-Arylisocoumarins: A mixture of homophthalic anhydride (1 mole), phenolic compound (1.1 mole) and commercial-polyphosphoric acid (8 parts) was heated at 120-30° for one hour. The reaction mixture was worked up as reported in the previous communication¹ to afford 3-arylisocoumarins.

W-(2'-carboxyphenyl)-acetophenones: 3-Arylisocoumarin on treatment with aqueous sodium hydroxide (10%) and subsequent acidification furnished the keto acid. This could be cyclised back to original isocoumarin in the presence of acid.

3-Aryl-3, 4-dihydroisocoumarins: Reduction of the above keto acids in ethanolic sodiumhydroxide with sodiumborohydride yielded the corresponding dihydroisocoumarins.

Conversion of 3-aryl-3, 4-dihydroisocoumarins into 3-arylisocoumarins: A mixture of 3-aryl-3, 4-dihydroisocoumarin (1 mole), N-bromosuccinimide (1.1 mole) and benzoylperoxide (0.02-0.04g) in appropriate solvent (dry carbontetrachloride or dry benzene) on refluxing near an illuminated 60 watt lamp for about 4 hours gave 4-bromoderivatives which were not purified. Subsequent treatment of the 4-bromoderivatives with either triethyl amine or pyridine resulted in dehydrobromination providing respective 3-arylisocoumarins.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express gratitude to Dr. A. B. Lal, Prof. and Head of the department of Chemistry for providing research facilities. We are also grateful to Dr. O. P. Jha and Dr. A. Mishra for recording I. R. and U. V. Spectra.

References

1. B. K. SARKHEL and JAGADISH N. SRIVASTAVA; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 915.

pH Metric Study of Complexes of Some Metal Ions with Salicylaldehyde-4-*m*-Chlorophenyl-3-Thiosemicarbazone

Y. N. BHATT, K. K. PATEL, K. J. SHAH* & R. S. PATEL

Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Bhavnagar.

Manuscript received 12 July 1976, revised 17 January 1977,
accepted 27 July 1977

LIGANDS such as thiosemicarbazones are studied to a limited extent pH-metrically. Here salicylaldehyde-4-*m*-Cl phenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone *m*-Cl-SPT derivative is studied with metal like VO²⁺, Cu²⁺, Co²⁺,

* For correspondence.

Ni²⁺. The formation constants for their metal were calculated by Calvin and Wilson pH titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti. The stability constants are determined in 50% aqueous dioxane medium.

Experimental

The ligand salicylaldehyde-4-*m*-chlorophenyl-3-thiosemicarbazone C₆H₄Cl.NH.C.N : CH.OH.C₆H₄

was synthesized and crystallised to get analytically pure (m.p. 181°)¹. The solution of *m*-Cl-SPT was prepared in dioxane (BDH, ANALAR grade) which was further purified by standard method of Vogel². Metal nitrates used were of AnalaR grade which were estimated by standard gravimetric and volumetric methods. Philips pH meter was used for pH measurements. pH meter was calibrated with buffer solutions having pH 4.33 and 9.1 at 25° ± 1°.

All titrations were carried out in a 100 ml. beaker kept in water thermostat maintained at 25° ± 1°. Thirty five to forty five readings were taken in each case. Each titration was repeated to get reproducible results. The metal ligand ratio was maintained 1:5. The acid, reagent and metal titrations were carried out with 0.2 M NaOH and 50% v/v dioxane: water. The solution for blank titration contained 0.004 M HNO₃ and 0.1 M KNO₃. The solution for ligand titration contained 0.001 M ligand in addition to the blank solution. The solution for metal titration contained 0.0002 M metal ion [0.0001 M for Co(II)] in addition to the ligand solution.

Results and Discussions

The practical proton-ligand stability constant for the ligand was calculated with the help of $\bar{n}_H$ values at different B values (pH meter readings in 50% aqueous dioxane-medium). $\bar{n}_H$ is calculated by the method of Irving & Rossotti³ as adopted by Jabalpurwala et al.⁴. Plot of $\log \frac{\bar{n}_H}{1-\bar{n}_H}$ against B is done to obtain a best straight line. From this straight line the values of the practical proton-ligand stability constant was obtained using the relation

$$\log P_{K_1}H = B + \log \frac{\bar{n}_H}{1-\bar{n}_H}$$

The proton ligand stability constant obtained is 9.55. For metal ligand stability constants $\bar{n}$ and pL were calculated by the method of Jabalpurwala et al.⁵. The values of $\bar{n}$ are plotted against pL. The values of $\log K_1$ were calculated by half integral method. The formation curve is given in Fig. 1. But for calculation of $\log K_2$ least square method⁶ in which $\frac{\bar{n}}{(1-\bar{n})HL}$ was

plotted against $\frac{(\bar{n}-2)HL}{(1-\bar{n})}$ and Olerup's method was also

used as there was not much difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$. The average stability constant are given Table-1.

Fig. 1

TABLE I

Metal	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$	σ
Cu^{2+}	9.96 ± 0.05	—	—	—
Co^{2+}	9.35 ± 0.05	9.38 ± 0.05	18.24 ± 0.05	0.063 ± 0.005
VO^{2+}	9.76 ± 0.05	—	—	—
Ni^{2+}	8.33 ± 0.05	—	—	—
H^+	9.55 ± 0.05	—	—	—

To check the validity of the results obtained by different methods for Co^{2+} , the $\bar{n}$ was recalculated taking $\log K_1$ and $\log \beta_2$ of least squares method as standard. There was not much difference between $\bar{n}$ calc. & $\bar{n}$ exptl. The value of σ standard deviation is 0.063.

For $\log K_1$, it is observed that stability constants are in the order $\text{VO(II)} > \text{Cu(II)} > \text{Co(II)} > \text{Ni(II)}$.

Thus, Irving-Williams rule is obeyed except for the position of Co(II) . This may be due to orbital stabilization of Co(II) complex.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. K. A. Thaker, Professor and Head, Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Bhavnagar, for providing laboratory facilities; to C. S. I. R., New Delhi and Gujarat State for the award of scholarships to Y. N. B. and K.K.P. respectively.

References

- I. D. SHAH and J. P. TRIVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, 889.
- A. I. VOGEL, "A Text book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans, 1961, p. 177.
- H. IRVING and H. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
- K. E. JABALPURWALLA, K. E. VENKATACHALAM and M. B. KABADI, *J. Inorg Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, 266, 1011.
- H. IRVING and H. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
- H. OLERUP, "Järnkloridernas Komplexbildning (diss.)", Lindstedts universitets-Bokhandel, Lund, (1944).